

Measuring the Efficiency of Innovative Logistics Projects' Resilience: ePIcenter project Experience

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Abstract - This paper explores the role of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in measuring the efficiency of resilience efforts in ensuring operations of project demonstrators and showcases, using the Horizon 2020 ePIcenter project as a case study. Resilience, the ability to withstand and recover from disruptions, is crucial for the functioning of large project-based systems. However, assessing the effectiveness of resilience initiatives remains a challenge. By reviewing literature, case studies, and best practices, this paper identifies and proposes a set of KPIs that capture key dimensions of resilience. The research aims to inform policymakers and stakeholders about the strengths and weaknesses of current resilience strategies, enabling better resource allocation and targeted improvements. The findings contribute to the development of robust and adaptive innovative logistics projects, promoting sustainable economic growth.

Keywords – KPI, resilience, Horizon 2020, ePIcenter

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era marked by increasing globalization and interconnectedness, innovative logistics models stemming from R&D projects play a pivotal role in facilitating global trade and economic growth. New critical nodes, routes and models of transportation and logistics networks are not only responsible for ensuring the smooth flow of goods but also serve as key economic hubs, generating employment opportunities and fostering regional development. However, the vulnerability of project demonstrators and showcases to various disruptions, both natural and man-made, poses significant challenges to their continued efficiency and functionality.

The Horizon ePIcenter project is a research and innovation project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program. The project aims to develop and test new technologies and solutions to improve the efficiency and sustainability of global freight transportation. The project is focused on the visibility – it will develop new ways to make supply chains more transparent and efficient by sharing data and information between different actors in the supply chain; and the optimisation - it will develop new algorithms and simulation tools to optimise the planning and routing of

freight transportation. The goals of the Horizon ePIcenter project are the following:

- To develop new data-driven solutions for visibility and transparency in supply chains, and to develop new optimization algorithms and simulation tools for freight transportation planning;
- To develop new technologies for the efficient and sustainable movement of empty containers; and demonstrate the benefits of the project's solutions in real-world use cases.

The ePIcenter project is spearheading three groundbreaking demonstrators to transform global logistics: ePI-Link, ePI-Node, and Arctic. These ambitious demonstrators aim to optimize multimodal freight flows, enhance multimodal transfer zone efficiency, and establish wildlife-friendly Arctic shipping routes. ePI-Link seeks to integrate global and TEN-T networks, comprising physical, logistics, and information layers, to optimize multimodal freight flows across Europe, North America, and China. ePI-Node focuses on optimizing multimodal transfer zones, the critical hubs where different transportation modes converge. It examines the potential of emerging technologies such as Hyperloop, autonomous vehicles, and AI optimization algorithms to streamline freight movement through these nodes, ultimately enhancing the overall efficiency of the global supply chain. Finally, The Arctic Demonstrator addresses the challenge of wildlife-friendly Arctic shipping while exploring sustainable new logistics routes. Employing ePIcenter's methodologies and solutions, the project aims to minimize the environmental impact of logistics operations in the Arctic by leveraging AI and Big Data technologies. [1].

In recent years, the concept of resilience has gained substantial attention as a means to address the vulnerabilities faced by critical infrastructure. Resilience refers to the ability of a system to withstand shocks, adapt to changing conditions, and recover quickly from disruptions [2]. Efforts to enhance resilience involve a range of activities, such as infrastructure improvements [3], risk assessment and management, operational redundancies, and collaborative partnerships among

stakeholders [4]. To ensure that limited resources are allocated optimally, and strategic decisions are made, it is crucial to have robust and meaningful Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that provide a comprehensive understanding of the resilience performance.

This paper aims to explore the role of KPIs in measuring the efficiency of resilience efforts in ePICenter demonstrators and showcases. By analysing existing literature, case studies, and best practices from different similar projects worldwide, the authors seek to identify and propose a set of KPIs that capture the key dimensions of resilience and enable stakeholders to assess the effectiveness of their resilience strategies. This paper strives to contribute to the ongoing efforts aimed at building robust and adaptive demonstrators and showcases capable of withstanding disruptions and fostering sustainable economic growth.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: RESILIENCE DETERMINANTS

Resilience, as applied to ePICenter demonstrators, encompasses the ability of these interconnected systems to withstand disruptions, adapt to changing circumstances, and recover swiftly while maintaining the efficient flow of goods and services. It entails a holistic understanding of the underlying ecosystem, including physical infrastructure, logistical networks, operational processes, and stakeholder collaborations.

To develop a comprehensive conceptual framework for measuring resilience, it is essential to identify and understand its key dimensions. These dimensions are shown in Figure 1.

The following dimensions provide a basis for assessing resilience and serve as foundational elements for the subsequent discussion on KPIs:

- *Infrastructure Resilience* [3]: This dimension focuses on the robustness and redundancy of physical infrastructure within the perimeter. It encompasses the durability and adaptive capacity of buildings, terminals, transportation networks, and critical utilities, aiming to minimize the impact of disruptions and enable rapid recovery.

Figure 1. Resilience dimensions

- *Operational Resilience* [5]: Operational resilience relates to the ability of the demonstrator's infrastructure to maintain and adapt their operations during disruptions. It includes factors such as operational flexibility, redundancies, and contingency plans, which allow for the continuation of essential processes and mitigate the effects of disruptions on trade flows.
- *Adaptive Capacity* [6]: Adaptive capacity refers to the demonstrator's infrastructure ability to anticipate and proactively respond to changing circumstances and emerging risks. It involves the capacity to learn from past events, foster innovation, and implement adaptive strategies that enhance the ability to withstand future disruptions.
- *Risk Management*: Risk management encompasses the identification, assessment, and mitigation of risks faced by the demonstrator. It involves robust risk assessment methodologies, proactive risk mitigation strategies, and effective emergency response plans to minimize the impacts of disruptions and expedite recovery.
- *Inter-Organizational Coordination* [4]: Effective coordination among various stakeholders within the demonstrator's ecosystem is crucial for resilience. This dimension focuses on the collaboration and information-sharing mechanisms among involved authorities, terminal operators, shipping lines, logistics providers, government agencies, and other relevant entities to ensure coordinated response efforts during disruptions.

To assess the efficiency of resilience efforts, the development and utilization of appropriate KPIs are crucial. KPIs provide quantifiable means to evaluate the performance of various resilience dimensions and determine the effectiveness of strategies implemented. By tracking specific metrics and benchmarks, KPIs enable stakeholders to measure progress, identify gaps, and allocate resources efficiently.

III. CHALLENGES TO THE DEMONSTRATORS' RESILIENCE

Resilience in previously described ePICenter demonstrators faces a multitude of challenges, arising from both internal and external factors. Addressing these challenges is vital for effective resilience planning and implementation. Such events can cause extensive damage, disrupt operations, and prolong recovery periods. Mitigating vulnerability and enhancing the resilience of physical assets against natural hazards is a crucial challenge. Understanding and addressing these challenges is important for effective resilience planning and implementation. The following are the main challenges that complex logistics projects encounter:

- *Vulnerability to Natural Disasters*: Logistics clusters, often located in coastal areas or near major water bodies, are susceptible to a range of natural disasters such as hurricanes, tsunamis, earthquakes, and flooding. These events can cause significant damage to the infrastructure, disrupt operations, and lead to

prolonged recovery periods [7]. The challenge lies in developing strategies to minimize vulnerability and enhance the resilience of physical assets in the face of such natural hazards.

- *Climate Change and Rising Sea Levels* [8]: Climate change poses a long-term challenge to logistics clusters. Rising sea levels, extreme weather events, and changing weather patterns impact operations, navigation, and infrastructure. Adapting to these changing conditions requires sustainable and climate-resilient infrastructure, advanced forecasting and monitoring systems, and the integration of climate considerations into resilience planning.
- *Cybersecurity and Digital Threats*: With the increasing reliance on digital systems and technologies, logistics clusters are exposed to cybersecurity risks and digital threats [9]. Cyberattacks targeting critical infrastructure, data breaches, and system failures can severely disrupt operations and compromise the resilience of the entire cluster. Robust cybersecurity measures, including information sharing and incident response protocols, are essential for protecting logistics clusters from these emerging threats [10].
- *Global Supply Chain Disruptions*: Chosen demonstrators are integral components of global supply chains, and disruptions in one part of the chain can have ripple effects on the entire system. Events such as trade disputes, geopolitical tensions, economic crises, and pandemics can disrupt the flow of goods, lead to congestion, and strain the capacity of the demonstrators [2]. Building resilience in the face of these complex and interconnected challenges requires enhanced collaboration, contingency planning, and the development of adaptive strategies.
- *Limited Resources and Competing Priorities*: Allocating resources effectively and prioritizing resilience investments is a significant challenge for the demonstrators [2]. Limited funding, competing priorities for infrastructure development, and conflicting stakeholder interests can hinder the implementation of comprehensive resilience measures [11]. Balancing short-term economic considerations with long-term resilience goals requires strategic planning, advocacy for funding, and stakeholder alignment.
- *Coordination and Collaboration*: Achieving resilience of complex pilot projects requires collaboration and coordination among various stakeholders, including involved authorities, logistics service operators, shipping lines, government agencies, and local communities [4]. The challenge lies in establishing effective governance structures, information-sharing mechanisms, and collaborative platforms to facilitate coordinated decision-making, resource sharing, and joint response efforts.

Addressing these challenges requires a holistic and integrated approach to sustainable and resilient planning [12]. By acknowledging these vulnerabilities and working towards solutions, stakeholders can enhance the capacity

of the demonstrators to withstand and recover from disruptions, ensuring the continuity of trade and economic activities.

IV. ROLE OF KPIS IN MEASURING RESILIENCE EFFICIENCY

KPIs play a critical role in measuring the efficiency of resilience efforts. These indicators provide stakeholders with quantifiable metrics to evaluate the performance of various dimensions of resilience and assess the effectiveness of strategies implemented [13]. KPIs serve as valuable tools for the authorities, terminal operators, shipping lines, logistics providers, and other stakeholders involved in demonstrator operations to monitor, analyse, and improve resilience outcomes [14].

Selecting the right KPIs for measuring sustainability and resilience is essential to obtain meaningful insights into its efficiency. The selection process involves considering the specific context, objectives, and stakeholder perspectives. KPIs should encompass a range of dimensions that capture the unique characteristics of port operations, infrastructure, and logistics. These dimensions may include but are not limited to infrastructure resilience, operational performance, adaptive capacity, risk management, and inter-organizational coordination.

Once the relevant KPIs have been identified, defining the metrics and measurement methodologies associated with each KPI is crucial for accurate evaluation [15]. This step involves determining data sources, establishing baselines, setting performance thresholds, and defining the frequency and scope of data collection. Metrics may include quantitative measurements, such as downtime duration, throughput capacity, or response time, as well as qualitative assessments, such as stakeholder satisfaction surveys or expert evaluations.

Effective utilization of KPIs requires collaboration among various stakeholders in the immediate demonstrators' ecosystems [16]. Authorities, terminal operators, shipping lines, logistics providers, and government agencies must collaborate to define common objectives, establish data-sharing mechanisms, and agree upon performance benchmarks. This collaborative approach ensures a holistic and integrated assessment of resilience and fosters collective responsibility for its improvement.

However, challenges may arise, such as data availability and reliability, ensuring consistency in metrics across stakeholders, and balancing the need for transparency with the protection of sensitive information. ePICenter demonstrators will operate in a dynamic and evolving environment, and the resilience of these complex systems must adapt accordingly. The selection and application of KPIs should evolve over time to address emerging challenges and capture changing stakeholder needs. By leveraging KPIs, stakeholders can assess the efficiency of their resilience efforts, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions to enhance overall resilience, fostering accountability, and continuous improvement. Relevant KPIs can be divided into several categories, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: ePICenter resilience KPIs

A. Sustainability KPIs

Sustainability encompasses three crucial aspects: economic, environmental, and social [17]. In terms of economic sustainability, responsible production of goods and services is key.

Economic KPIs that can be utilized include total costs (covering e.g., transportation costs, costs related to cargo handling, expenses due to prolonged waiting time, fuel consumption, staff costs, etc.), the complete profit derived from transportation, Estimated Time of Arrival, loading and unloading capabilities, as well as storage capacity [18].

The environmental sustainability aspect focuses on maintaining the quality and reproducibility of natural resources [17]. Hristov et al. [19] mentioned various environmental KPIs such as use of returnable containers, total direct or indirect greenhouse gas emissions by weight, reduced CO₂ emissions per fleet, renewable sources rate, waste reduction rate, efficiency resources use rate, reduced fuel energy, etc. T. P. V. Zis et al. [20] claimed that ship operators may use sensors to monitor emissions live or, more commonly, sailing patterns from ship schedules or Automatic Identification System (AIS) data, coupled with weather data, to estimate fuel consumption and emissions.

Regarding social sustainability, there is scarce literature addressing this specific subject and implementing social sustainability in traditional freight transportation practices is challenging [21]. KPIs that could monitor the social aspect of sustainability are [22], [23]: average employee overtime hours, integration rate, sick leave rate, stakeholder satisfaction rate, average age of employees, etc.

Some KPIs fall into more aspects, such as: the economic and environmental aspects (e.g. additional revenue due to recycling [19]), social and environmental (e.g., linking mortality with shipping emissions [20]) or economic and social aspects (e.g. health and safety prevention costs [24]).

Enhancing the overall resiliency of a supply chain requires comprehensive visibility, open information sharing, strong trust relationships, proactive risk management strategies, collaborative partnerships, adaptable processes, agile response mechanisms, and rapid decision [16].

B. Security and Safety KPIs

One important element of resilience is security (including the security from cyber-attacks or physical attacks). For example, the evaluation of KPIs related to cyber threats lacks a sufficiently elaborated systematic approach [25].

To measure the resilience element of security, several KPIs can be utilized related to IT Systems Sustain/Recovery Attack, which can be measured using various metrics [26]. For example, *Mean time between downtime/failures* metric measures the average time that a system functions without experiencing downtime or failure. A longer average uptime indicates higher system reliability. Furthermore, *Percentage difference in downtime/failure* metric assesses the variation in downtime or failure rates across different system operations [26]. If certain operations experience significantly more downtime or failures than others, it may indicate a need for targeted improvements or remediation strategies.

Average repair time metric quantifies the average duration required to address a problem and restore full system functionality [26]. Shorter average repair times suggest more efficient and effective problem-solving processes. *Percentage difference in repair time* metric evaluates the percentage change in the average time taken to resolve system issues. A consistent decrease in repair time indicates ongoing improvement and optimization of problem-solving mechanisms [26]. However, Agyepong, E. et al. [25] mentioned the importance of assessing analysts' performance as well.

C. Visibility and Information Sharing KPIs:

Information on the location, vessels and cargo is crucial for timely decision-making and proactive risk mitigation in the supply chain [27].

The key performance indicator for visibility in the supply chain is Information Level, which measures the extent to which assets can be monitored. A high Information Level indicates that all relevant assets are being tracked and their movements are visible to decision-makers.

The KPI for the quality of data is important for ensuring the accuracy and timeliness of information. Sources of data, such as sensors, RFID tags, and real-time updates should be very reliable and consistent. Data quality metrics should include error rates and the number of empty values, which represent missing information [28].

Information sharing is essential for building resilient supply chains. Communication technology KPIs assess the type of technology used for sharing information across the network. EDI systems, telephone calls, faxes, and

other communication tools should be integrated and efficient to facilitate information exchange.

Organizational culture KPIs evaluate the openness and transparency of information sharing within the supply chain. A culture of collaboration and trust fosters effective information exchange and enables timely problem-solving.

V. DISCUSSION

The research findings reveal several important aspects that need to be considered when assessing and improving resilience. Firstly, it is evident that the resilience of complex demonstrators such as those deployed as a part of ePCenter project is a multidimensional concept that encompasses various dimensions, including infrastructure resilience, operational resilience, adaptive capacity, risk management, and inter-organizational coordination. These dimensions highlight the interconnectedness and complexity of the demonstrators' ecosystems and emphasize the need for a comprehensive approach to resilience assessment process. The identified dimensions serve as foundational elements for developing meaningful KPIs that capture the key aspects of resilience and provide a holistic understanding of the demonstrators' performance.

Furthermore, the discussion on KPIs highlights the importance of selecting appropriate metrics and measurement methodologies for accurate evaluation. The selection process should consider the specific context, objectives, and stakeholders, striking a balance between quantitative and qualitative indicators.

However, the utilization of KPIs in assessing resilience also poses challenges. Data availability and reliability remain key issues, requiring standardized data collection processes and robust data-sharing mechanisms. Ensuring consistency in metrics across different stakeholders and maintaining a balance between transparency and the protection of sensitive information is another challenge. In the discourse on enhancing the resilience of innovative logistics projects, the connection between sustainability and resilience emerges as a critical consideration.

Sustainability, with its focus on environmental integrity, economic viability, and social equity, forms a foundational pillar that supports and amplifies resilience efforts. The ePCenter project's commitment to developing sustainable logistics solutions underscores this connection. Sustainable practices not only mitigate the environmental impact of logistics operations but also enhance their resilience by reducing vulnerability to disruptions, fostering economic stability, and ensuring social wellbeing. By prioritizing sustainability, the ePCenter project not only aims to achieve its immediate objectives but also contributes to building a logistics infrastructure that is robust, adaptable, and capable of withstanding and recovering from future challenges. This synergistic relationship between sustainability and resilience underscores the importance of an integrated approach, where the pursuit of sustainability enhances resilience capabilities, thereby ensuring the long-term success and viability of innovative logistics projects.

VI. CONCLUSION

Resilience, as applied to complex demonstrator projects, encompasses the ability of these interconnected systems to withstand disruptions, adapt to changing circumstances, and recover swiftly while maintaining the efficient flow of goods and services. It involves various dimensions, including infrastructure resilience, operational resilience, adaptive capacity, risk management, and inter-organizational coordination. To measure the efficiency of resilience efforts, appropriate KPIs are crucial. KPIs provide quantifiable means to evaluate the performance of these resilience dimensions and determine the effectiveness of strategies implemented.

The selection of suitable KPIs for measuring resilience requires considering the specific context, objectives, and stakeholder perspectives. These KPIs should capture both tangible and intangible aspects of resilience, striking a balance between quantitative and qualitative indicators. Defining the metrics and measurement methodologies associated with each KPI is essential to ensure accurate evaluation. This involves determining data sources, establishing baselines, setting performance thresholds, and defining the frequency and scope of data collection.

The utilization of KPIs in assessing demonstrators' resilience offers several benefits. It enables stakeholders to objectively evaluate the efficiency of resilience strategies, benchmark performance against industry standards, and identify best practices. KPIs also facilitate evidence-based decision-making, resource allocation, and the prioritization of resilience investments. However, challenges may arise, such as data availability and reliability, consistency in metrics across stakeholders, and balancing the need for transparency with the protection of sensitive information.

Effective utilization of KPIs requires collaboration among various stakeholders in the demonstrators' ecosystem. Local authorities, terminal operators, shipping lines, logistics providers, government agencies and other stakeholders must collaborate to define common objectives, establish data-sharing mechanisms, and agree upon performance benchmarks. This collaborative approach ensures a holistic and integrated assessment of resilience and fosters collective responsibility for its improvement.

While the use of KPIs is beneficial, the selection and application of these indicators should evolve over time to address emerging challenges and capture changing stakeholder needs. ePcenter demonstrators operate in a dynamic and evolving environment, and the resilience of these clusters must adapt accordingly. Regular review and refinement of KPIs ensure their relevance and effectiveness in measuring resilience as the demonstrators and the industry continue to evolve. By leveraging KPIs, stakeholders can assess the efficiency of their resilience efforts, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions to enhance overall resilience. The utilization of KPIs fosters collaboration, accountability, and continuous improvement of resilience.

In conclusion, this paper has explored the role of KPIs in measuring the efficiency of resilience efforts of

ePICenter demonstrators and showcases. Through an analysis of existing literature and best practices, the paper has identified the importance of robust and meaningful KPIs in assessing the effectiveness of resilience strategies. The selection, definition, and application of KPIs require collaboration among stakeholders and consideration of the specific context and objectives of each demonstrator. By adopting a systematic and standardized approach to measuring resilience efficiency, stakeholders can allocate resources optimally, prioritize investments, and implement targeted improvements to enhance overall resilience. This research contributes to the ongoing efforts aimed at building robust and adaptive complex logistics systems capable of withstanding disruptions and fostering sustainable economic growth.

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